

Ultra-high vacuum cleaver for the preparation of ionic crystal surfaces

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Cleaving single crystals *in-situ* under ultra-high vacuum conditions provides a reliable and straightforward approach to prepare clean and atomically well-defined surfaces. Here, we present a versatile sample cleaver to efficiently prepare ionic crystals under ultra-high vacuum conditions, which is suitable for preparation of softer materials such as alkali halides and harder materials such as metal oxides. One of the advantages of the presented cleaver design is that the cleaving blade and anvil to support the crystal are incorporated into the device. Therefore, no particularly strong mechanical manipulator is needed, and it is compatible with existing vacuum chambers equipped with an xyz-manipulator. We demonstrate atomically flat terraces and the atomic structure of NaCl(001), KBr(001), NiO(001), and MgO(001) cleavage planes prepared *in-situ* under ultra-high vacuum conditions and imaged by low-temperature non-contact atomic force microscopy.

Since in ambient conditions ionic crystal surfaces, in particular metal oxides, suffer from immediate adsorption of water and other contaminants, *in-situ* preparation under ultra-high vacuum (UHV) conditions is required to obtain well-defined surfaces for surface science studies. Cleaving provides a reliable and straightforward approach for obtaining clean and atomically well-defined ionic crystal surfaces. Therefore, several different sample cleaver devices and sample holders designs have been previously reported for UHV surface science studies.[1–5] However, some cleaver implementations are not very versatile, e.g. they use spring-loaded blades, which can only be used once before reopening the UHV chamber, [2] and others are mostly suitable for soft crystals [5].

The versatile sample cleaver presented here has the advantage that the cleaving blade and anvil to support the crystal are integrated into the device, while the sample sits on the sample manipulator. Therefore, no particularly strong mechanical manipulator is needed. Additionally, the cleavage directly on the manipulator has the advantage that the sample holder design is flexible such that glued, screwed, or clamped crystals are possible to be cleaved. Second, the sample can be annealed directly after cleavage to reduce surface charges, which may result from the cleaving process. Moreover, the compact design is compatible with most existing vacuum chambers with a xyz-transfer stage and a CF40-flange perpendicular to it. The presented cleaving device was optimized for an Omicron XA type preparation chamber (Scienta Omicron GmbH) to allow for the efficient preparation of atomically smooth ionic crystal surfaces, i.e. alkali halides and metal oxides, in UHV. We show the well-defined surface structure of cleaved NaCl(001), KBr(001), NiO(001), and MgO(001) surfaces using non-contact atomic force microscopy (nc-AFM), which demonstrates that the design of the presented cleaver is also suitable for very hard crystals.

Fig. 1 shows in detail the setup of the cleavage device and the sample holder used. The cleavage device consists of two main parts: a movable tungsten carbide blade and a basket. The basket collects the cleaved crystal part and supports the backside of the crystal while cleaving with the incorporated anvil. The cleaving blade is mounted on a linear z-shift with a 25 mm range (Fig. 1a-b). The blade rod is supported within

the bore of the basket to improve rigidity and positioning during the cleaving process. The part of the blade rod that moves through the hole has a triangular shape to minimize friction. We used a tungsten carbide blade (Lutz Blades) with a 30° shaped edge. Therefore, the cleavage force is applied to a single point, which is more suitable for cleaving hard crystals such as MgO, as a perfect alignment between the blade and the crystal plane is less crucial, and the cleavage requires less force.[6] Furthermore, the blade touches only one corner of the freshly cleaved sample and for less than a millimeter, minimizing the damage caused by the blade on the sample.

FIG. 1. Setup of the cleaving device. (a) Overview drawing of the cleaving device (top view). (b-c) Photographic picture of the cleaving device mounted on the UHV chamber and (c) front part with the stainless-steel basket, anvil, and blade outside UHV. (d-e) Drawing and photographic picture of the used sample holder (screws are not shown) with an MgO sample ($3 \times 4 \times 5 \text{ mm}^3$).

The basket is mounted via three support rods on the back flange (CF40) of a 100 mm z-shift, which allows the device to be moved in and out of the center of the vacuum chamber. Due to the flange size, the diameter of the device is limited to approximately 37 mm. The height of the anvil is precisely adjusted to balance the stabilization of the sample and minimize the wasted amount of crystal material. However, the cleavage becomes unstable if the anvil is too low because a torque is exerted on the sample. The anvil width has been reduced compared to the rest of the basket to avoid interference and damage to other parts of the manipulator that sit next to the sample. Moreover, the anvil is screwed on the basket and is interchangeable to easily adapt it to any changes, e.g. the sample holder or preferred sample thickness.

The design of the sample holder allows many possibilities, as long as the sample is freely accessible on the top part. We used a sample holder based on a modified standard flag style sample plate (e.g. Omicron, Specs) similar to the design proposed by Barth et al. [3], see Fig. 1d-e. Thereby, a stainless steel frame (2 mm high) with an inner rectangular extrusion of (6 mm x 5 mm) is mounted on the plate. The crystal is fixed by a headless screw (A in Fig. 1d), which presses the crystal against the wall of the holder. Optionally, to avoid a drop-down of the sample after thermal annealing and cooling down for nc-AFM measurements, a 0.25 mm diameter tungsten wire is used, which is inserted through two holes in the stainless steel frame and a drilled hole through the sample (B in Fig. 1d). The standard dimensions for the used crystals are around 2.5 mm x 2 mm x 3.5 mm (length x width x thickness) before cleavage. Thicker crystals can be cleaved multiple times.

In Fig. 2, the different steps of the cleaving process are outlined. First, the device is moved into the center of the chamber, i.e. below the sample, see Fig. 2a. Thus, the sample sits on the manipulator, with the crystal surface facing downward, roughly centered between the blade and the anvil. Next, the lateral position of the manipulator is adjusted so that the sample is positioned roughly in line with the blade rod. While the blade is still retracted, the sample can be moved downward with the manipulator z-shift. Meanwhile, the z-shift of the cleaver with the basket is fine adjusted at the same time until the top site of the sample holder frame touches the anvil (Fig. 2c). The contact between the sample holder and the anvil is confirmed by measuring the resistance *via* a multimeter. It is recommended that the cleaving device z-shift is now slightly moved out to ensure that the anvil touches and fully supports the backside of the crystal. At this point, if a second cleave of the crystal is planned, given that the crystal's thickness allows for multiple cleaves, one should retract the manipulator z-shift by 2 - 4 mm. Next, the blade rod is extended via the 25 mm z-shift until the blade touches the crystal (Fig. 2d). Upon cleaving, the top part of the crystal falls off of its own into the basket. At this point, the movement of the blade should be stopped immediately to ensure that the fresh surface remains unaffected and does not get scratched by the blade.

Nc-AFM measurements were carried out in a UHV system ($< 1 \cdot 10^{-10}$ mbar) composed of a preparation cham-

FIG. 2. Schematic drawings of the cleaving process: (a) Lateral alignment of the manipulator with respect to the cleaver. (b) Side view depicting the sample holder approaching the anvil. (c-d) Side and top view of the cleavage process (basket is transparent).

ber, where the cleaver is attached, and an analysis chamber, equipped with a commercial low-temperature STM/nc-AFM (Scienta Omicron GmbH) operated at liquid helium temperature (4.78 K). Nc-AFM data was recorded in the frequency-modulation mode operated at a constant amplitude A using a Nanonis OC4 phase-locked loop (PLL) from SPECS GmbH and HF2LI from Zurich Instruments. qPlus tuning fork sensors [7] ($k=1800$ N/m, $Q=19'000-35'000$) with etched W tips were used. *In-situ* tip preparation was performed by gently poking into an atomically defined metal surface (prepared by Ar^+ sputtering and annealing cycles) prior to imaging the cleaved bulk insulator surfaces. AFM measurements under ambient conditions are performed with an MFP-3D microscope (Asylum Research) in tapping mode. The AFM images were analyzed using the WSxM software.[8]

After cleavage in UHV, most surfaces of ionic crystals are charged and require annealing before high-resolution nc-AFM measurements of the freshly cleaved surface are possible.[6, 9, 10] The indicated sample temperatures for annealing were measured *via* a thermocouple close to the sample. The charging of the sample and the resulting long-range electrostatic force contribution was monitored by measuring Kelvin parabolas. To compensate for the contact potential difference, a bias voltage was applied at the sample or tip. The applied voltage was set to the apex of the frequency shift vs. bias voltage parabola.

Fig. 3 shows atomic force microscopy images of typical cleaved MgO(001), NiO(001), KBr(001), and NaCl(001) surfaces. First, we explored the cleaving of hard crystals such as the metal oxides MgO(001) and NiO(001). We cleaved and imaged some crystals under ambient conditions to determine the step structure of the cleavage plane of MgO (SurfaceNet GmbH, 4 x 3 x 25 mm³ rods) on a large scale, see Fig. 3a-b. We observed high-quality surfaces without any debris from cleaving. *In-situ* cleaved MgO(001) surfaces were prepared by annealing typically at 410 °C and 390 °C for 3 h, respectively, prior and after cleavage.[6] This procedure eliminated the charge from cleaving and atomic resolution was readily obtained on a clean surface (Fig. 3c). NiO(001) (SurfaceNet GmbH, 2 x 2 x 10 mm³ rods) surfaces were prepared *in-situ* in UHV in a similar way by annealing typically at 360 °C for 1 h before and after cleaving. Overview nc-AFM images show monatomic steps and pits with large terraces, respectively, re-

FIG. 3. Atomic force microscopy images of cleaved MgO(001), NiO(001), KBr(001), and NaCl(001). (a-b) Large-scale topographic AM-AFM image of a MgO(001) cleavage face with corresponding height section after cleavage and measuring under ambient conditions. (c) Atomic resolution nc-AFM image of an UHV-cleaved MgO(001) surface. (d-h) Large-scale topographic and atomic resolution nc-AFM images of UHV-cleaved (d-f) NiO(001), (g-h) NaCl(001), and (i) KBr(001). nc-AFM parameter: (c) $df = -2.0$ Hz, $f_0 = 21.85$ kHz, $A = 1$ nm; (d-e) $df = -2.0$ Hz, $f_0 = 24.45$ kHz, $A = 0.6$ nm; (f) $df = -18.0$ Hz, $f_0 = 24.45$ kHz, $A = 0.15$ nm; (g) $df = -1$ Hz, $f_0 = 25.45$ kHz, $A = 0.8$ nm; (h) $df = -27.3$ Hz, $f_0 = 24.47$ kHz, $A = 0.12$ nm; (i) $df = -7.7$ Hz, $f_0 = 22.45$ kHz, $A = 0.15$ nm.

sulting in an atomically clean surface, Fig. 3d. Zoomed-in nc-AFM images of NiO(001) cleavage planes (Fig. 3e-f) revealed a low defect density, and atomic resolution images were reproducibly obtained.

Finally, we investigated in Fig. 3g-h softer alkali halide surfaces, i.e. NaCl(001) and KBr(001) (Korth Kristalle GmbH).

Both alkali halide surfaces were prepared by *in-situ* cleavage with prior and subsequent annealing (typically at 150-180 °C for 60-90 min) to remove charges. The preparation leads to atomically clean surfaces with well-defined wide terraces (> 200 nm in width) and atomic resolution is readily obtained.

In conclusion, we present a compact cleaving device where the sample is cleaved directly on the manipulator and both the anvil and blade are incorporated into the cleaver. Therefore, the cleaving device provides ample flexibility on the sample side, no particularly strong mechanical manipulator is needed, and it is compatible with existing UHV chambers equipped with an xyz-manipulator. On the basis of low-temperature nc-AFM experiments on NaCl(001), KBr(001), NiO(001), and MgO(001), we demonstrate that the cleaver is suitable for the preparation of softer materials such as alkali halides and harder materials such as metal oxides in UHV. The cleavage planes on all surfaces had large terraces and atomic resolution was also readily obtained. Hence, these surfaces are ideally suited for molecular self-assembly studies and other surface science experiments using high-resolution nc-AFM in ultra-high vacuum.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the finding of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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